

Research Article

Vitamin D Deficiency in Adults Attending an Outpatient Clinic: A Cross-Sectional Study of Knowledge, Attitudes, and Supplement Use

Aybüke BACANLI¹ ¹ Department of Family Medicine, Prof. Dr. Cemil Taşcıoğlu City Hospital, University of Health Sciences, Istanbul, Türkiye

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Submitted April 23

Accepted May 21

Publication June 30

Keywords

Vitamin D Deficiency

Awareness

Dietary Supplement Use

Outpatient Clinic

ORCID iDs of the Corresponding:

Aybüke BACANLI,
0000-0003-1836-194X

ABSTRACT

Objective: Vitamin D deficiency is a major global public health concern. Despite its high prevalence, community awareness and knowledge remain insufficient. This study aimed to determine knowledge, attitudes, and supplement use patterns regarding vitamin D deficiency among adults attending a family medicine outpatient clinic

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study enrolled 310 adults attending a tertiary hospital outpatient clinic in Istanbul (January–June 2019). Data were collected via structured questionnaire (minimum required sample size was 285; 95% CI, 5% margin of error). Chi-square, Fisher's exact test, Mann-Whitney U, Kruskal-Wallis tests, and Spearman correlation were applied; $p < 0.05$ was accepted as significant

Results: Of 310 participants (61.6% female; median age 36, range 18–75 years), 54.8% reported ever having used a vitamin D supplement, predominantly upon physician prescription. Among those with prior measurement ($n=180$), 91.1% had deficiency or insufficiency (finding limited to this subgroup). Women supplemented more than men (66.5% vs 36.1%; $p < 0.001$); chronic disease ($p < 0.001$) and regular medication use ($p < 0.001$) were significantly associated with supplementation. Deficiency was more prevalent in non-working individuals (94.8% vs 89.3%; $p = 0.016$). Knowledge score did not differ significantly by sex ($p = 0.094$), age ($p = 0.847$), education ($p = 0.128$), or supplement use ($p = 0.056$).

Conclusion: Vitamin D deficiency was highly prevalent in the measured subgroup while specific misconceptions regarding dietary sources persisted despite relatively high scores on basic knowledge items. These findings underscore the need for structured patient education and systematic screening strategies in outpatient clinical settings

Doi:

Co-Author ORCID IDs:
Seçil ARICA
Professor

0000-0003-0135-6909

Corresponding author:

Aybüke BACANLI

aybuke.bacanli@gmail.com

Introduction

Vitamin D is a fat-soluble sterol compound that functions as a prohormone. Beyond its classical roles in calcium-phosphorus metabolism and bone mineralization, its potential association with cardiovascular diseases, metabolic syndrome, autoimmune disorders, and various cancers has been extensively documented (Holick et al., 2011). Vitamin D deficiency is now recognized as a global public health problem (Cui et al., 2023).

A pooled analysis of 7.9 million participants reported global prevalence of vitamin D deficiency of 15.7% (Cui et al., 2023). A retrospective study of 11,734 adults in Bursa, Turkey found that deficiency was widespread, with significantly lower serum levels in women (Göktaş et al., 2020). A community-based cross-sectional study conducted in Tokat province found serum levels below 20 ng/mL in more than 85% of participants (Katar et al., 2026). Despite this high prevalence, community awareness and knowledge of vitamin D deficiency remain insufficient. Studies assessing knowledge in Turkey have predominantly focused on specific groups such as pregnant women or rural populations, and data covering the general adult outpatient population are limited (Boz et al., 2019; Kurt et al., 2015). A cross-sectional study of 713 adults in a rural setting (Kırşehir) found that fewer than 50% were aware of vitamin D deficiency, with awareness significantly lower in older and less-educated individuals (Kurt et al., 2015). Unlike previous studies that focused on specific groups such as pregnant women or rural populations, this study addresses a gap by examining these dimensions in an unselected adult outpatient population attending a tertiary-level family medicine clinic. The aim was to determine the level of knowledge, attitudes, and supplement use patterns regarding vitamin D deficiency, and to identify clinically actionable targets for structured education and systematic screening within the outpatient setting.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Sample

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted with adults aged 18 years and over attending the outpatient clinic of Prof. Dr. Cemil Taşcıoğlu City Hospital (formerly Okmeydanı Training and Research Hospital), a tertiary hospital in Istanbul, between January and June 2019. Inclusion criteria were: age ≥ 18 years, absence of communication difficulties, and provision of verbal informed consent. Individuals with cognitive impairment that prevented completion of the questionnaire were excluded. Participation was voluntary.

The minimum required sample size was calculated as 285, based on a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, and a 50% expected prevalence of vitamin D-related knowledge gaps, using the standard formula for cross-sectional studies: $n = z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1-p) / e^2$. A total of 310 participants were enrolled to account for potential incomplete responses.

Data Collection

A structured questionnaire consisting of 26 items was developed through a review of current literature and expert consultation. Expert review was conducted with three specialist physicians (two family medicine specialists and one endocrinologist); questions were revised for clarity and content validity based on their feedback. A pilot application was conducted with 20 participants prior to the main study; minor wording adjustments were made accordingly. The questionnaire covered sociodemographic characteristics, chronic disease and medication use, vitamin D measurement status and results, supplement use habits, sunscreen use, knowledge of dietary sources, and four knowledge items. Each knowledge item was scored as 1 point; total knowledge score ranged from 0 to 4.

Vitamin D Level Classification

Vitamin D status categories were defined according to the 2011 Endocrine Society Clinical Practice Guideline, which was the prevailing guideline during the study period (Holick et al., 2011): deficiency as serum 25(OH)D <20 ng/mL, insufficiency as 20–29 ng/mL, and sufficiency as ≥30 ng/mL. Severe deficiency was defined as <12 ng/mL. These categories were applied to the self-reported prior measurement results in the measured subgroup (n=180).

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Normality of continuous variables was assessed with the Shapiro-Wilk test. The Mann-Whitney U test and Kruskal-Wallis test were used for non-normally distributed continuous variables; the independent samples t-test was used where normality was met. The relationship between age and knowledge score was examined using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. Categorical variables were analyzed with the chi-square test, or Fisher's exact test when expected cell counts were below 5. Statistical significance was set at p<0.05. This study was reported in accordance with the STROBE statement.

Ethics Approval and Informed Consent

This study was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of University of Health Sciences Okmeydanı Training and Research Hospital (Approval No: 1359, Date: 25.06.2019). Verbal informed consent was obtained from all participants. The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Results

Sociodemographic Characteristics

A total of 310 participants were enrolled; 61.6% (n=191) were female and 38.4% (n=119) were male. Median age was 36 (18–75) years. University-level education or above was reported by 61.3% (n=190). Chronic disease was present in 28.1% (n=87); hypertension was the most common (n=26, 29.9% of chronic disease cases), followed by thyroid disease (n=21, 24.1%). Regular medication use was reported by 31.6% (n=98). Demographic and clinical characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Vitamin D Measurement and Deficiency

58% of participants (n=180) had previously had their vitamin D levels measured. Among this measured subgroup, 91.1% (n=164) had deficiency or insufficiency; severe deficiency (<12 ng/mL) was present in 39.4% (n=71), and only 8.9% (n=16) had sufficient levels. This finding applies only to the measured subgroup and should not be generalized to all 310 participants, as this group was likely enriched for symptomatic individuals.

Supplement Use Patterns

Overall, 54.8% (n=170) of participants reported ever having used a vitamin D supplement. Among users, 91.2% (n=161) initiated supplementation upon physician prescription; 7.1% (n=12) started following television or internet information. Drops were the most common form (69.4%, n=118), followed by ampoules (21.2%, n=36) and capsules (8.2%, n=14). 64% of users reported daily use and 16% weekly use. Fatigue/weakness (58%) and muscle pain (20%) were the most commonly reported reasons for initiating supplementation. Sex was significantly associated with supplement use: 66.5% of women used supplements compared with 36.1% of men (chi-square, p<0.001; crude OR=3.51, 95% CI: 2.17–5.67). Among those with chronic disease, 78.2% used supplements versus 45.7% of those without (p<0.001; crude

OR=4.25, 95% CI: 2.39–7.53). Among regular medication users, 74.5% used supplements compared with 45.8% of non-users (p<0.001; crude OR=3.48, 95% CI: 2.02–6.00). Age group (p=0.172), education (p=0.322), and employment status (p=0.275; employed: 120/211, 56.9% vs unemployed: 50/99, 50.5%) were not significantly associated with supplement use. Detailed data are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Demographic and clinical characteristics of participants (n=310)

Variable	Category	n	%
Sex	Female	191	61.6
	Male	119	38.4
Education	Illiterate	1	0.3
	Primary school	34	11.0
	Middle school	24	7.7
	High school	61	19.7
Chronic disease	University or above	190	61.3
	Present	87	28.1
Regular medication	Absent	223	71.9
	Yes	98	31.6
Age – median (min–max)	No	212	68.4
	36 years (18–75)		

Values represent frequencies and percentages unless otherwise stated. Percentages are based on column totals

Table 2. Factors associated with vitamin D supplement use (n=310)

Variable	Category (n)	Users n/N (%)	Non-users n/N (%)	p
Sex	Female (191)	127/191 (66.5%)	64/191 (33.5%)	<0.001*
	Male (119)	43/119 (36.1%)	76/119 (63.9%)	
Chronic disease	Present (87)	68/87 (78.2%)	19/87 (21.8%)	<0.001*
	Absent (223)	102/223 (45.7%)	121/223 (54.3%)	
Regular medication	Yes (98)	73/98 (74.5%)	25/98 (25.5%)	<0.001*

Variable	Category (n)	Users n/N (%)	Non-users n/N (%)	p
	No (212)	97/212 (45.8%)	115/212 (54.2%)	
Age group	18–49 years (257)	136/257 (52.9%)	121/257 (47.1%)	0.172
	50–75 years (53)	34/53 (64.2%)	19/53 (35.8%)	
Employment	Employed (211)	120/211 (56.9%)	91/211 (43.1%)	0.275
	Unemployed (99)	50/99 (50.5%)	49/99 (49.5%)	

*Chi-square test; $p < 0.05$. OR: crude odds ratio calculated by binary logistic regression (unadjusted). Percentages are based on row totals.

Factors Associated with Vitamin D Level (Measured Subgroup, n=180)

In the measured subgroup, deficiency/insufficiency was significantly more common in women (93.3%) than in men (84.4%) (chi-square, $p = 0.04$). The deficiency rate was 94.8% in unemployed individuals versus 89.3% in employed individuals ($p = 0.016$). Age group ($p = 0.625$), sunscreen use (Fisher's exact, $p = 0.110$), chronic disease ($p = 0.561$), and regular medication use ($p = 0.389$) were not significantly associated with vitamin D level (Table 3).

Knowledge of Vitamin D

61.3% of participants ($n = 190$) reported general awareness of the effects of vitamin D deficiency. Women scored significantly higher than men on the bone development item (92.1% vs 84.0%; $p = 0.022$). The 18–50 age group scored significantly higher than the 50–75 group on bone development (90.2% vs 77.1%; $p = 0.013$) and immune function items (79.9% vs 66.7%; $p = 0.044$). Detailed response rates by sex and age are shown in Table 4.

Regarding vitamin D-rich foods, milk (20.8%) and eggs (20.5%) were the most frequently reported sources. Fatty fish were recognized by only 17.5%. Spinach, which contains negligible vitamin D, was incorrectly identified by 11.0%; 14.5% could not name any source.

The total knowledge score (0–4) was not normally distributed (Shapiro-Wilk, $p < 0.001$); median was 4.0 (IQR: 3–4). No significant correlation was found between knowledge score and age (Spearman $r = 0.011$; $p = 0.847$). No statistically significant association was found between knowledge score and sex (Mann-Whitney U, $p = 0.094$), education (Kruskal-Wallis, $p = 0.128$), or supplement use (Mann-Whitney U, $p = 0.056$).

Table 3. Factors associated with vitamin D level (measured subgroup, $n = 180$)

Variable	Category (n)	Sufficient n/N (%)	Deficient/Insufficient n/N (%)	p
Sex	Female (135)	9/135 (6.7%)	126/135 (93.3%)	0.04*
	Male (45)	7/45 (15.6%)	38/45 (84.4%)	
Employment	Employed (122)	13/122 (10.7%)	109/122 (89.3%)	0.016*
	Unemployed (58)	3/58 (5.2%)	55/58 (94.8%)	
Age group	18–49 (147)	13/147 (8.8%)	134/147 (91.2%)	0.625
	50–75 (33)	3/33 (9.1%)	30/33 (90.9%)	
Sunscreen use	Always/Often (45)	3/45 (6.7%)	42/45 (93.3%)	0.110†
	Rarely/Never (135)	13/135 (9.6%)	122/135 (90.4%)	
Chronic disease	Present (87)	4/87 (4.6%)	83/87 (95.4%)	0.561
	Absent (93)	12/93 (12.9%)	81/93 (87.1%)	
Regular medication	Yes (70)	4/70 (5.7%)	66/70 (94.3%)	0.389
	No (110)	12/110 (10.9%)	98/110 (89.1%)	

*Chi-square test; †Fisher's exact test; $p < 0.05$. Percentages are based on row totals. This table applies only to the 180 participants who had previously had vitamin D levels measured.

Table 4. Correct response rates for knowledge items by sex and age group

Knowledge item	Male %	Female %	18-50 %	50-75 %	p*
Vitamin D is important for bone development	84.0	92.1	90.2	77.1	0.013†
Vitamin D is important for immune function	77.3	79.1	79.9	66.7	0.044†
Sunlight prevents vitamin D deficiency	84.9	86.4	84.5	83.3	0.808
Vitamin D deficiency causes muscle pain/fatigue	84.0	89.5	87.9	81.3	0.226

*Chi-square test; †p<0.05.

Discussion

This study evaluated vitamin D knowledge, attitudes, and supplement use patterns among 310 adults attending a family medicine outpatient clinic in Istanbul. The 91.1% deficiency/insufficiency rate in the measured subgroup appears high; however, this group consisted of individuals who had actively sought vitamin D testing, likely due to clinical symptoms, and the rate cannot be generalized to the overall sample. Community-based data from Turkey present a similar picture: a retrospective study of 11,734 adults in Bursa reported a deficiency rate of 66.4% (Göktaş et al., 2020); a community-based cross-sectional study in Tokat province found rates exceeding 85% (Katar et al., 2026).

The high prevalence in the measured subgroup may be attributed to widespread adoption of an indoor lifestyle despite abundant sunlight in Turkey, limited consumption of fatty fish, and insufficient inclusion of vitamin D-rich foods in the diet. The significantly higher deficiency rate in women (93.3% vs 84.4%; p=0.04) may be explained by clothing habits, cultural restrictions on sun exposure, and hormonal differences (Ciarambino et al., 2023).

The higher supplement use among those with chronic disease (78.2% vs 45.7%; p<0.001) and among regular medication users (74.5% vs 45.8%; p<0.001) is likely explained by multiple converging mechanisms. First, increased frequency of clinical contact provides repeated opportunities for physician counselling and laboratory screening. Second, individuals managing a chronic condition may develop greater health literacy and self-monitoring motivation over time.

Third, access to the healthcare system — including specialist referrals and regular follow-up appointments — facilitates both testing and prescription. Taken together, these findings suggest that vitamin D supplementation in this population is largely clinician-mediated rather than self-initiated, consistent with data from the UK outpatient setting (Tanna et al., 2023). The significantly higher deficiency rate in unemployed individuals (94.8% vs 89.3%; p=0.016) may reflect reduced outdoor activity and more time spent indoors (Telo et al., 2017), as well as potentially lower engagement with preventive healthcare. The lack of a significant association between sunscreen use and vitamin D level may be related to the fact that 65.8% of participants never used sunscreen — a finding that limits statistical contrast.

Scores on basic knowledge items were relatively high (median 4.0 out of 4; Shapiro-Wilk p<0.001), yet specific misconceptions persisted — notably the poor recognition of dietary sources. The total knowledge score did not differ significantly by any demographic variable. The poor recognition of fatty fish as a vitamin D source (17.5%) and the erroneous identification of spinach (11.0%) are consistent with findings from knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) studies in other countries (Kwabena et al., 2025). The dominant role of physician prescription confirms the key position of outpatient physicians in vitamin D management (Tanna et al., 2023).

These findings suggest that opportunistic screening during routine outpatient visits may be an effective strategy, particularly given that the measured subgroup in this study — patients who had already undergone testing, likely due to symptoms — showed a 91.1% deficiency/insufficiency rate. This rate should not be extrapolated to the unscreened general outpatient population; however, it does indicate that targeted screening among symptomatic or high-risk patients would likely yield a high diagnostic yield. Vitamin D screening should be prioritized for patients with chronic disease, regular medication use, or relevant symptoms such as fatigue or musculoskeletal pain.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. The single-centre design limits generalizability. Self-reported questionnaire data are susceptible to recall and social desirability bias. Most importantly, vitamin D serum levels were available only for the 180 participants who had voluntarily undergone prior testing; this subgroup is not representative of the full sample, and the 91.1% deficiency rate should not be generalized. The knowledge assessment based on only four items may have limited measurement sensitivity; although this section was not intended as a formal scale, absence of psychometric data (e.g. internal consistency) is acknowledged as a limitation. Future studies should include biochemical measurements in all participants, adopt multi-centre designs, and use validated knowledge instruments.

Conclusion

A high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency was detected in the measured subgroup; this finding applies specifically to patients who had undergone prior testing and should not be generalized to the broader outpatient population. The determinant roles of sex and chronic disease on supplement use, the higher deficiency rate in unemployed individuals, and persistent misconceptions regarding dietary sources all point to concrete targets for clinical action. Practically, family physicians in outpatient settings could integrate a brief vitamin D risk-factor checklist into routine consultations to identify candidates for targeted testing. Point-of-care educational materials emphasising fatty fish, egg yolk, and fortified dairy as dietary sources of vitamin D — and correcting the misconception that spinach is a source — could be incorporated into waiting-room resources. The predominant role of physician prescription reinforces that the outpatient encounter is the primary leverage point for both counselling and appropriate supplementation. Larger, multi-centre studies including biochemical measurements in all participants are warranted.

Declaration of conflicting interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

This research received no funding from any public, commercial, or non-profit organization.

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Author Contributions

A.B.: Conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. S.A.: Conceptualization, supervision, writing – review & editing. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

Acknowledgements

We thank all participants who agreed to take part in this study. This article was derived from the residency thesis of Dr. Aybke BACANLI, completed under the supervision of Prof.Dr. Seil ARICA at the Department of Family Medicine, University of Health Sciences Okmeydanı Training and Research Hospital (2020).

References

- Boz, İ., Teskereci, G., & ner, F. . (2019). Gebelik ve doęum sonu dnemdeki kadınların D vitamini ve gneşlenme ile ilgili farkındalık dzeylerinin belirlenmesi: Kesitsel bir alıřma [Determining awareness levels regarding vitamin D and sun exposure in pregnant and postpartum women: A cross-sectional study]. *Jinekoloji-Obstetrik ve Neonatoloji Tıp Dergisi*, 16(3), 116-121.
- Ciarambino, T., Crispino, P., Minervini, G., & Giordano, M. (2023). Vitamin D: Can gender medicine have a role? *Biomedicines*, 11(6), Article 1762. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines11061762>
- Cui, A., Zhang, T., Xiao, P., Fan, Z., Wang, H., & Zhuang, Y. (2023). Global and regional prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in population-based studies from 2000 to 2022: A pooled analysis of 7.9 million participants. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 10, Article 1070808. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2023.1070808>
- Fidan, F., Alkan, B. M., & Tosun, A. (2014). aęın pandemisi: D vitamini eksiklięi ve yetersizlięi [The pandemic of the era: Vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency]. *Trk Osteoporoz Dergisi*, 20(2), 71-74.
- Gktař, O., Ersoy, C., Ercan, İ., & Can, F. E. (2020). Vitamin D status in the adult population of Bursa, Turkey. *European Journal of General Practice*, 26(1), 156-162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13814788.2020.1846712>
- Grant, W. B., Wimalawansa, S. J., Pludowski, P., & Cheng, R. Z. (2025). Vitamin D: Evidence-based health benefits and recommendations for population guidelines. *Nutrients*, 17(2), Article 277. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu17020277>
- Holick, M. F., Binkley, N. C., Bischoff-Ferrari, H. A., Gordon, C. M., Hanley, D. A., Heaney, R. P., Murad, M. H., & Weaver, C. M. (2011). Evaluation, treatment, and prevention of vitamin D deficiency: An Endocrine Society clinical practice guideline. *The Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 96(7), 1911-1930. <https://doi.org/10.1210/jc.2011-0385>
- Katar, M., ıtıl, R., nder, Y., & Demir, O. (2026). Prevalence of vitamin D deficiency and related factors among adults in Tokat province, Trkiye. *Acta Biochimica Polonica*, 72, Article 15459. <https://doi.org/10.3389/abp.2025.15459>
- Kurt, E. E., Koak, F. A., Erdem, H. R., Tuncay, F., & Kıranatlıoęlu, F. (2015). Kırsal blgede D vitamini farkındalıęının deęerlendirilmesi: Kesitsel bir alıřma [Assessment of vitamin D awareness in a rural area: A cross-sectional study]. *Fiziksel Tıp ve Rehabilitasyon Bilimleri Dergisi*, 18(3), 176-181.
- Kwabena, A. A., Appiah, B., Danso, S. A., Agomuo, S. K. S., Kwarteng, S., Senu, E., Effah, A., Sakyi, S. A., & Fondjo, L. A. (2025). Knowledge, attitude and practices regarding vitamin D among adults in Ghana: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*, 25(1), Article 212. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-025-21370-x>
- Tanna, N. K., Karki, M., Webber, I., Alaa, A., El-Osta, A., & Blair, M. (2023). Knowledge, attitudes, and practices associated with vitamin D supplementation: A cross-sectional online community survey of adults in the UK. *PLoS ONE*, 18(8), Article e0281172. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0281172>
- Telo, S., Kaman, D., & Akgl, G. (2017). Elazıę ilinde D vitamini dzeylerinin yař, cinsiyet ve mevsimlere gre deęiřimi [Variation of vitamin D levels by age, sex, and season in Elazıę province]. *Fırat Tıp Dergisi*, 22(3), 130-134.